

Variability of the UV luminosity function with SPICE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the variability of the UV luminosity function recently detected by JWST in high-redshift galaxies, utilizing the SPICE simulation suite to examine the influence of various supernova (SN) feedback models. We analyze three distinct feedback scenarios: *bursty-sn*, *smooth-sn*, and *hyper-sn*, each uniquely affecting star formation rates and UV luminosities. Notably, the *smooth-sn* model, characterized by gentler SN feedback, produces the highest intrinsic luminosities, up to 0.4 dex brighter across redshifts due to its relatively weaker feedback. In contrast, the *bursty-sn* model, defined by intense and episodic SN explosions, exhibits substantial variability with fluctuations reaching up to 2.5 in σ_{UV} , a proxy for quantifying UV LF variability. The *hyper-sn* model yields results that fall between these two extremes. A strong correlation between UV LF variability and dark matter halo mass is observed, with lower mass halos exhibiting greater variability, consistent with the expectation that SN feedback is more efficient in the shallower gravitational potential wells of low-mass halos. Our results, compared with observational data from JWST, show reasonable agreement, although the limited simulation box size constrains the capture of the bright end of the LF. This study underscores the critical role of SN feedback in shaping the UV LF and highlights the mass and redshift dependence of its variability, suggesting that UV LF variability may account for the exceptionally bright galaxies observed by JWST at high redshifts.

Key words: galaxies: formation – galaxies: kinematics and dynamics – galaxies: luminosity function, mass function – galaxies: star formation – (stars:) supernovae: general

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) started to provide breakthrough results in July 2022, our understanding of the early galaxy formation process has been challenged. Although over the past decade the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) enabled us to observe galaxies out to $z \approx 10$ (Zheng et al. 2012; Coe et al. 2013; Oesch et al. 2016; Morishita et al. 2018; Bagley et al. 2022), JWST has pushed our observational barrier to even higher redshifts, and has detected an unexpected overabundance of massive galaxies at $z > 10$ (Castellano et al. 2022; Finkelstein et al. 2022; Naidu et al. 2022; Adams et al. 2023; Morishita & Stiavelli 2023; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Donnan et al. 2023a; Atek et al. 2023; Pérez-González et al. 2023; Willott et al. 2024; Donnan et al. 2024). This discovery might challenge theoretical models, as it suggests a high incidence of bright galaxies at this epoch which cannot always be explained (Mason et al. 2023; Boylan-Kolchin 2023; Lovell et al. 2023). The recent detection of a spectroscopically confirmed galaxy at $z = 14.32$ by Helton et al. (2024) significantly elevates the challenge, as it pushes the existence of bright objects to even higher redshifts. Such observations raise several intriguing questions: What are the physical properties of the early galaxies? What is their formation history? Do these findings create tensions with the standard Λ CDM cosmology?

With these puzzling observations, one topic that has attracted significant attention is the UV luminosity function (LF) of early galaxies, and a lively debate is on-going regarding the origin of its variability and boosted bright end. A few potential physical processes have been suggested to explain these discoveries. One of them is an increased star formation efficiency (SFE) due to a weaker feedback which could boost the abundance of UV-bright galaxies by forming more stars per baryon (Fukushima & Yajima 2022; Inayoshi et al. 2022; Dekel et al. 2023; Harikane et al. 2023). Also, a more top-heavy initial mass function (IMF) could lead to a high abundance of early bright galaxies by producing more UV photons per unit of stellar mass formed (Inayoshi et al. 2022; Yung et al. 2023; Chon et al. 2024; Steinhart et al. 2023; Cueto et al. 2024). The interplay between dust attenuation and the abundance of massive halos at high redshifts could lead to a mild evolution of the UV LF. While this alone cannot fully explain the abundance of high-redshift bright galaxies (Ferrara et al. 2023; Mirocha & Furlanetto 2023), radiation pressure on dust may contribute to the reduction of the attenuation (Fiore et al. 2023; Ferrara et al. 2024). Other authors explore a possible cosmological origin, including a modified primordial power spectrum (Hirano & Yoshida 2023; Padmanabhan & Loeb 2023; Parashari & Laha 2023; Sabti et al. 2023), primordial non-Gaussianity (Biagetti et al. 2023), and alternative dark matter scenarios (Bird et al. 2023; Dayal & Giri 2023; Gong et al. 2023).

A promising natural explanation for the variability in the UV

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Figure 1. 1500 Å luminosity functions at $z = 12, 10, 8, 6$ (from top left to bottom right) for three feedback models (in different colors). Solid and dashed curves refer to intrinsic and dust attenuated LFs, respectively. A compilation of observations from HST and JWST (Finkelstein et al. 2015; Bouwens et al. 2015; Harikane et al. 2022; Naidu et al. 2022; Adams et al. 2023; Harikane et al. 2023; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Leung et al. 2023; Donnan et al. 2023b,c; Pérez-González et al. 2023; Casey et al. 2024; Robertson et al. 2024; McLeod et al. 2024) is shown as gray data points.

luminosities of galaxies, instead, is a strong stochasticity of star formation. Indeed, the cycles of gas inflow from the cosmic web and outflow due to feedback or mergers can easily affect the galactic environment, causing a stochastic behaviour in the star formation rate (SFR) as suggested by several authors (Hopkins 2014; Domínguez et al. 2015; Muratov et al. 2015; Sparre et al. 2017; Faucher-Giguère 2018; Pallottini & Ferrara 2023), and hence a variability of the UV LF (Sparre et al. 2017; Furlanetto & Mirocha 2022; Sun et al. 2023).

In this paper, we investigate the impact of SFR variability on the LF of high- z galaxies using the suite of radiation hydrodynamic simulations SPICE (Bhagwat et al. 2024, hereafter B24), which comprises three different implementations of supernova (SN) feedback (while the rest of the simulation setup is the same), which result in a different level of burstiness and in a variety of star formation histories. This allows us to systematically quantify the SFR and UV LF variability.

Specifically, we introduce the simulations in Section 2, the results are presented in Section 3, while in Section 4 we summarise our conclusions and future prospects. Throughout the paper, we adopt a flat Λ CDM cosmology consistent with Planck Collaboration et al. (2016) with $\Omega_m = 0.3099$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.6901$, $\Omega_b = 0.0489$, $h = 0.6774$, $\sigma_8 = 0.8159$ and $n_s = 0.9682$, where the symbols have their usual meaning.

2 THE SPICE SIMULATION SUITE

In order to investigate the impact of SN feedback onto galaxy properties, we post-process the suite of radiation-hydrodynamical simulations SPICE (B24), which we briefly introduce below.

SPICE has been performed with RAMSES-RT (Rosdahl et al. 2013; Rosdahl & Teyssier 2015), the radiation-hydrodynamics extension

Figure 2. Evolution of dust attenuated UV LF in 10 Myr interval centered at $z \approx 10$ in three different SN feedback models - bursty-sn, smooth-sn, hyper-sn from top to bottom panel.

of the Eulerian Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) code RAMSES (Teyssier 2002). The simulations target a comoving cubic box of size $10 h^{-1} cMpc$ with 512^3 dark matter particles of mean mass $m_{dm} = 6.38 \times 10^5 M_\odot$. The AMR allows each parent gas cell to split into 8 smaller cells when certain conditions are met (see B24). As a reference, this provides a physical resolution ranging from 4.8 kpc at $z = 5$ for the coarsest level ($\ell_{min} = 9$) down to approximately 28 pc at $z = 5$ for the finest level ($\ell_{max} = 16$). The hydrodynamical equations are solved using a second order Godonov scheme and the dynamics of collisionless dark matter and stellar particles are computed by solving the Poisson equation with a particle-mesh solver, projecting onto a grid using the Cloud-in-Cell scheme (Guillet & Teyssier 2011). Gas cooling and heating are accounted for as in Rosdahl et al. (2013). Star-formation has been modelled following Kretschmer & Teyssier (2020), which adopt a subgrid turbulence model depending on the

Figure 3. Temporal evolution of the SFR averaged over 2 Myr accounting for all stellar particles inside the virial radius of the most massive halo at $z = 5$, which has a total stellar mass of $3.34 \times 10^9 M_\odot$, $1.97 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ and $2.05 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ for the *bursty-sn*, *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* model, respectively. Colors refer to the different SN feedback models. In the inset, we show the distributions of δ_{SFR} , together with the corresponding standard deviation, σ_{SFR} (see text for the details of the calculation).

physical conditions of each computational cell including parameters like the local gas turbulent Mach number and the virial parameter, which acts as a measure of the gravitational balance in the region, and which results in a spatially-variable star formation efficiency. Additionally, SPICE includes a radiative transfer scheme with five frequency groups, i.e. infrared (0.1-1 eV), optical (1-13.6 eV), and three UV (13.6-24.59 eV; 24.59-54.42 eV; 54.42- ∞ eV).

To correctly capture the momentum injection into the cells due to supernova feedback, the scheme presented in Kimm et al. (2015) is adopted. Keeping all the parameters for momentum injection constant, different simulations have been run based on the timing of supernova events and the amount of energy injected. We briefly present the different feedback models as follows:

- **"bursty-sn"**: each stellar particle experiences a single event of SN explosions at a fixed timescale of 10 Myr, equivalent to the mean time at which SN occurs for the adopted Chabrier (2003) initial mass function. An energy of 2×10^{51} ergs per SN explosion is injected into the neighbouring cells.

- **"smooth-sn"**: for a given stellar population, a SN with mass $> 20 M_\odot$ can explode as early as 3 Myr, whereas SN with progenitor mass of $8 M_\odot$ can explode as late as 40 Myr. An energy of 2×10^{51} ergs per SN explosion is injected into the neighbouring cells.

- **"hyper-sn"**: SN explosions happen at different times as in *smooth-sn*, with the injected energy extracted stochastically from a normal distribution centered at 1.2×10^{51} ergs and ranging from 10^{50} ergs to 2×10^{51} ergs (see also, Sukhbold et al. 2016; Diaz-Rodríguez et al. 2018, 2021). Additionally, a metallicity dependent fraction of SN explodes as Hypernovae (HN), with an energy injection of 10^{52} ergs.

Dust in SPICE is not modelled as an active ingredient but rather through a direct dependence on the local gas-phase properties, i.e. its metallicity and ionization state. Following Nickerson et al. (2018), the dust number density is computed as $n_d = (Z/Z_\odot) f_d n_H$, where Z represents the local metallicity, $f_d = 1 - x_{\text{HII}}$ is the fraction of neutral hydrogen, and n_H is the hydrogen number density. This relation ensures that the dust density depends on both chemical enrichment and the local ionization conditions. Despite expectations of dust being typically destroyed in photo-ionized gas, observations have shown dust-to-ionized-gas ratios as high as 0.01. The quantity f_d permits non-zero dust effects even in ionized environments. The propagation of UV photons influences the gas via photo-ionization and photo-heating, but also through radiation pressure generated from both photo-ionization and through dust absorption. Infrared and optical photons interact with gas solely through radiation pressure on dust particles. Each photon group is characterized by specific dust absorption and scattering properties. When optical and UV photons are absorbed by dust, their energy is transferred to the infrared group, which later interacts with the gas through multi-scattering radiation pressure.

For a more comprehensive description of the simulations and the supernova feedback models discussed above, we refer the readers to B24.

3 RESULTS

In this Section, we present results from our analysis of how different SN feedback models affects the SFR and UV LF.

3.1 UV luminosity function

In Figure 1, we present the 1500 Å LF for all feedback models at various redshifts. The LFs have been derived from the stellar spectral energy distributions within a 10 Å bin centered around 1500 Å. The solid and dashed lines indicate the intrinsic and dust-attenuated luminosity functions, respectively. To account for dust attenuation, we utilize the Monte Carlo radiative transfer code RASCAS (Michel-Dansac et al. 2020). In this approach, 100 rays are cast from each stellar particle within a halo out to its virial radius. The dust attenuation along each ray is computed following the model described in the previous section.

It is clear that *smooth-sn* produces a higher intrinsic luminosity (by 0.3-0.4 dex) at all redshifts and magnitudes, mainly because of the larger number of galaxies obtained in this model. Conversely, at $z \gtrsim 10$ the *hyper-sn* model yields the lowest galaxy count across all magnitude bins. The decline in HN rate which occurs at lower redshift results in the increase in SFR and LF observed at $z \sim 8$, although this is no more visible at even lower redshifts. Notably, at $z \sim 6$ the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models give rise to exceptionally bright galaxies ($M_{1500} \lesssim -22$), although the box size of the simulations is not large enough to properly capture the high luminosity end of the LF. The *bursty-sn* model produces results which are typically in between those of the other models. The effect of dust attenuation (dashed curves) starts to be visible from an absolute magnitude of $M_{1500} \sim -16$, the value changing slightly depending on feedback model and redshift. When comparing the dust attenuated LFs to a compilation of observations from HST and JWST (Finkelstein et al. 2015; Bouwens et al. 2015; Harikane et al. 2022; Naidu et al. 2022; Adams et al. 2023; Harikane et al. 2023; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Leung et al. 2023; Donnan et al. 2023b,c; Pérez-González et al. 2023; Casey et al. 2024; Robertson et al. 2024; McLeod et al. 2024), we notice a fairly good match in the range of magnitudes covered by SPICE.

To investigate the temporal evolution of the dust-attenuated UV LF on short timescales, we present in Figure 2 the UV LF before and after a 10 Myr interval at redshift $z \approx 10$. In the *bursty-sn* model we observe that the fraction of objects with M_{UV} between -16 and -14 decreases slightly before and after the snapshot at $z \approx 10$, while the fraction increases for objects with $M_{UV} = -17$. This temporary shift in luminosity bins is primarily due to the interplay of SFR regulated by SN feedback and dust attenuation. In comparison, the *smooth-sn* model exhibits a more gradual and regular evolution of the UV LF, producing a steady increase in the number of most luminous objects (ie. $M_{UV} \leq -17$) with changing the number in the lower luminosity bins over time. This suggests a more stable star formation process in the *smooth-sn* model, although it is a primary understanding. Overall, we find that the *bursty-sn* model experiences more pronounced fluctuations in the UV LF. The *hyper-sn* model shows similar feature as *bursty-sn*, albeit less extreme, variations. In principle, this demonstrates that SN feedback plays a significant role in driving UV LF variability, particularly in bursty star formation environments. However, to quantify this effect more rigorously, we will delve deeper into the statistical analysis of SFR and UV LF in the following sections. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between SN feedback and UV LF evolution across different feedback models.

3.2 Star formation rate variability

In this Section, we explore how the different SN feedback models impact the variability of the SFR. Figure 3 shows the star formation

Figure 4. σ_{SFR} as a function of halo mass M_{halo} at different redshifts (indicated by the colorbar) for *bursty-sn* (top panel), *smooth-sn* (middle) and *hyper-sn* (bottom).

history of the most massive halo from the SPICE snapshot at $z = 5$ for all three models. We note that at this redshift the virial mass of the halo is $2.7 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ and the total stellar mass is $2.1 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$, $1.9 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ and $1.7 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ in the *bursty-sn*, *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* model, respectively. It is evident that overall *bursty-sn* produces the largest fluctuations in the SFR, with deviations of up to two orders of magnitude. In contrast, the *smooth-sn* model shows smaller fluctuations, which we expect to be the result of the less disruptive feedback, although other factors, such as the dynamical stabilization of the ISM by more massive bulges or differences in the gravitational potential, may also play a role. Notably, though, *smooth-sn* produces ~ 10 times more stars, reaching a SFR of $\sim 70 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. In the *hyper-sn* model, the SFR is the lowest during the first 200 Myr (i.e. for lookback times larger than 700 Myr), when the impact of HN explosions is the strongest. However, at later times the SFR becomes similar to that of *smooth-sn*, and in the final 100 Myr it exceeds *smooth-sn* by a factor of ~ 1.5 . The fluctuations in

Figure 5. Distribution of σ_{SFR} in different M_{halo} bins for the three SN feedback models, as indicated by the colors. Numbers refer to the corresponding average standard deviation.

hyper-sn are comparable to those in *smooth-sn*. It is important to note that while feedback plays a significant role in shaping the SFR and UVLF variability, other secondary factors, such as morphology, gravitational potential, and the turbulent state of the ISM, are also influential. In a follow-up paper, we plan to investigate the impact of these physical mechanisms.

To quantify the SFR variability, we compute the median star-formation main sequence obtained in bins of 100 Myr¹, $\text{SFR}_{\text{median}}$, together with the associated standard deviation. The calculation is performed using all halos at all redshifts in different halo mass bins. We then estimate the stochastic time variability of SFR defined as $\delta = \log_{10}(\text{SFR}/\text{SFR}_{\text{median}})$, which quantifies how the SFR devi-

¹ We additionally perform the same analysis using bin sizes of 30 and 50 Myr and find no qualitative differences in our conclusions.

Figure 6. Relation between $\sigma_{\text{UV}}^{\text{dust}}$ and M_{halo} in different redshift bins for three SN feedback models – *Left Panel* : *bursty-sn*, *Middle Panel* : *smooth-sn* and *Right Panel* : *hyper-sn*. The light to dark colorbars indicate high to low redshift bins.

ates from its median value. The SFR values are associated with the appropriate halo mass bins, ensuring that we accurately reflect the halo’s mass at any given time in our analysis. The distribution of δ_{SFR} for the most massive halo in each model is shown in the inset of figure 3, together with the corresponding standard deviation, σ . As anticipated, *bursty-sn* shows the widest distribution, with a σ which is more than double the one of *smooth-sn*, i.e. $\sigma_{\text{bu}} = 0.34$ and $\sigma_{\text{sm}} = 0.12$. The *hyper-sn* model produces a δ distribution which is similar to the one from the *smooth-sn* model, with a slightly higher standard deviation of $\sigma_{\text{hn}} = 0.14$.

In figure 4 we examine the mass dependence of σ_{SFR} at different redshifts. Typically, smaller halos exhibit a variability higher than more massive ones, suggesting a stronger effect of SN feedback on lower mass halos. For halos with $M_{\text{halo}} < 10^9 M_{\odot}$, all three models exhibit a similar redshift-dependent trend, with the variability decreasing at lower redshifts. This is primarily due to deeper potential

Figure 7. Distribution of $\sigma_{UV}^{\text{dust}}$ in different M_{halo} bins for the three SN feedback models, as indicated by the colors. Numbers refer to the corresponding average standard deviation.

wells, as well as to the suppression of cold gas supply in a highly photoionized environment, leading to a more secular star formation rate and, consequently, a lower σ_{SFR} . However, the bursty-sn model consistently shows higher scatter compared to the smooth-sn one, while the hyper-sn model results are in between. In higher mass bins, the trend reverses, with variability becoming increasingly merger-driven. In these more massive halos, cold gas is more vulnerable to ram-pressure stripping by hot gas from nearby halos. In the bursty-sn model, σ_{SFR} remains high and nearly mass-independent at lower redshifts, due to the combined effects of frequent supernova events and mergers. The behavior of the hyper-sn model is particularly interesting: while it mostly mirrors the smooth-sn model, it exhibits a spike in σ_{SFR} at the lowest redshifts for halos with masses around $10^{10.5} M_{\odot}$. Additionally, the formation of disks in galaxies around these low redshifts could be a consequence of the diminished

Figure 8. Dependence of $\sigma_{UV}^{\text{dust}}$ on the DM halo mass M_{halo} . The solid curves refer to the median value, while the shaded regions are the standard deviation. Colors refer to the different SN feedback models, while the dotted curve represents the fit from Gelli et al. (2024).

hypernova-driven feedback, a topic we plan to explore in a follow-up study.

Figure 5 presents the distribution of σ_{SFR} in three halo mass bins: $M_{\text{halo}} > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$, $10^9 M_{\odot} < M_{\text{halo}} \leq 10^{10} M_{\odot}$, and $M_{\text{halo}} \leq 10^9 M_{\odot}$. In the bursty-sn model, strong and regular fluctuations dominate the overall population, resulting in a σ_{SFR} distribution skewed towards higher values at all masses in comparison to smooth-sn. The hyper-sn model produces distributions that typically fall between those of the other two models, although they are much more similar to those of smooth-sn. In the highest mass bin, though, the hyper-sn model exhibits an even higher σ_{SFR} than the bursty-sn model, which aligns with the pronounced spike observed in Figure 4. For all models, the σ_{SFR} distributions are wider in the highest mass bin, indicating a broader range of star formation variability. As we move to lower mass halos, the distributions become progressively steeper, indicating a narrower range of variability but centered around higher σ_{SFR} values. Additionally, as noted earlier in Figure 4, the distributions for all models systematically shift towards higher σ_{SFR} values as halo mass decreases.

In the following section, we will explore how this mass and redshift-dependent SFR variability influences the variability of the UV LF.

3.3 Implications for UV luminosity

The variability in the bright part of the UV luminosity function is influenced by three primary factors: the accretion history of galaxies, feedback regulating the star formation rate, and dust attenuation (Shen et al. 2023). Variations in the accretion rate can lead to fluctuations in the amount of gas available for star formation, thereby influencing the UV luminosity. Feedback mechanisms, such as supernova explosions and stellar winds, can regulate star formation by heating the surrounding gas, expelling it from the galaxy and generating turbulence, causing intermittent bursts of star formation, and

Figure 9. Redshift evolution of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ for $M_{halo} < 10^9 M_{\odot}$ (dashed lines), $10^9 M_{\odot} < M_{halo} < 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (dotted) and $M_{halo} > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (solid). The curves for the entire sample are shown in solid curve with black edges. Colors refer to the three SN feedback models, while the values from observational and other theoretical studies are shown in grey data points and shaded regions.

thus contributing to the variability in UV luminosity. The impact of feedback on this burstiness is not linear, and feedback-driven dust destruction also plays a role. The combined effect of feedback and accretion history on the SFR is encapsulated in the term σ_{SFR} , which has been introduced in the previous section. As dust within galaxies absorbs UV light reducing the observed luminosity, variations in dust content and distribution can lead as well to changes in the observed UV luminosity.

To examine the variability of the UV luminosity function, we compute the scatter in luminosity around the median UV LF discussed in section 3.1. We note that, for a consistent comparison with previous literature, we primarily discuss the variability of the dust attenuated UV LF (σ_{UV}^{dust}). However, the dust-attenuated UV LF generally shows a variability higher than the one of its intrinsic counterpart, with the bursty-sn model exhibiting the largest deviation. Only in very few cases dust attenuation causes a slight reduction in variability. This analysis reveals that the fluctuations in the UV LF likely originate from differences in dust abundance over to the presence of low-density channels that allow more UV light to escape. Figure 6 shows σ_{UV}^{dust} as a function of M_{halo} in the range $z = 5 - 15$. At the highest redshifts, all models exhibit a similar dependence on mass, with smaller halos showing a larger UV LF variability because of the stronger effect of the SN feedback. As expected, the bursty-sn model has the highest variability. At $z \lesssim 10$, σ_{UV}^{dust} in the bursty-sn model starts to rise and reaches values as high as 2.5 for $M_{halo} \sim 10^{10.3} M_{\odot}$ at $z \approx 6.5$. This elevated variability in the bursty-sn model is driven by the combined effect of frequent SN-induced bursts and dust absorption. In comparison, in the other models σ_{UV}^{dust} never becomes larger than 1.5, and for smooth-sn it is always below 1.3. The hyper-sn model exhibits a variability comparable to the one in the

bursty-sn model until $z \approx 9$, and then the variability decreases as more galaxies evolve into rotationally-supported disk-like structures due to a reduction in the HN rate (we plan to explore this in details in a follow-up paper). As a consequence, the σ_{UV}^{dust} curves start to be more similar to those of the smooth-sn model. At $z < 6$ all models have nearly identical variability levels, although bursty-sn still shows slightly higher fluctuations.

Similarly to Figure 5, in Figure 7 we show the distribution of σ_{UV}^{dust} in different halo mass bins. As found for the SFR, the curves are shifted towards higher values of σ_{UV}^{dust} for smaller halo masses, with bursty-sn having the widest distribution and the highest peak value. The smooth-sn and hyper-sn show a similar distribution, with the exception of the intermediate mass regime, where the latter is fairly wider. The average σ_{UV}^{dust} reflects what discussed above, with the bursty-sn model having a value which increases with decreasing mass bin from 1.07 to 1.47, and many objects displaying values as high as $\gtrsim 1.5$. The maximum value reached in smooth-sn is about 1.5, with the average σ_{UV}^{dust} increasing from 0.57 to 1.10. The hyper-sn model falls in-between the other two, although it is much more similar to smooth-sn, as discussed also earlier. In the intermediate mass bin, though, the difference is more pronounced and can be attributed to variations in the energy injected per SN event and the occurrence of HN events, which increase the overall variability in σ_{UV}^{dust} .

In figure 8 we explore how the median σ_{UV}^{dust} depends on M_{halo} , where the former is calculated in each mass bin from all the curves in figure 6. We find that the median curves in all models have a similar slope. However, the bursty-sn model consistently produces higher values. Additionally, the scatter around the median differs among the models, and, as expected, the bursty-sn model shows the largest

scatter because of the wider range of variabilities in UV LF, while *smooth-sn* has the smallest. We also note the slope of our curves is consistent with the one from the analytical fit by Gelli et al. (2024) based on the results of the FIRE-2 simulation at $z \approx 8$ (Sun et al. 2023), although its value is matched only by the *bursty-sn* model.

Finally, in Figure 9 we explore the redshift evolution of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ in different halo mass bins, as well as the one computed over the full sample. We observe that in all models $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ is larger in the lowest mass bin, as smaller halos, with their shallower potential wells, are more sensitive to feedback effects. The curves for both the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models exhibit a clear and consistent trend across redshifts, with σ_{UV}^{dust} generally decreasing at lower redshifts. This is likely due to the reduced impact of feedback mechanisms as galaxies evolve, and their gravitational potentials deepen over time. In contrast, the *bursty-sn* curve shows a different pattern, with σ_{UV}^{dust} increasing from $z \approx 10$ to $z \approx 6$, followed by a decline thereafter. Furthermore, the evolution of σ_{UV}^{dust} varies across different mass bins and models, revealing distinct behaviors that merit closer investigation. Notably, across all masses and redshifts, the *bursty-sn* model consistently exhibits the highest average values of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$, indicating more pronounced fluctuations in star formation compared to the other models. The peak at $z \sim 6.3$ reaches a value of approximately 2.0, possibly marking the transition where supernova-driven bursts of star formation are balanced by the deeper gravitational potentials of galaxies, allowing for greater gas retention and heightened variability. Beyond this point, as galaxies grow more massive, SN feedback becomes less disruptive and the dust abundance increases, leading to a decline in UV luminosity function variability at lower redshifts. The only exception occurs at $z \gtrsim 10$ for halos with $M_{halo} > 10^9 M_{\odot}$, where the *hyper-sn* model produces the highest values because of the impact of the stronger HN explosions. On the other hand, the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models have a similar behaviour, with the latter typically providing slightly larger values of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$.

The results from our analysis of SPICE simulations are compared to values extracted from other observational (Ciesla et al. 2024) as well as theoretical (Muñoz et al. 2023; Mason et al. 2023; Shen et al. 2023; Pallottini & Ferrara 2023) studies. Employing a semi-empirical approach, Muñoz et al. (2023) found a value of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ as high as 2.5 at $z \sim 12$, which drops to below 0.8 at $z \leq 10$. While none of our models reproduces such large high- z values, at lower redshift there is a better agreement, although in this case our $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ are always slightly larger. Mason et al. (2023) utilized a fully empirical framework to predict that a $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ up to 1.5 in the range $8 < z < 10$ is necessary for models to align with existing observations. These numbers are in line with those predicted in our *bursty-sn* model. Following a similar methodology, Shen et al. (2023) found the much lower value of 0.75 at $z \approx 9$, which is instead consistent with those predicted by the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models. At $z \approx 10$ and 12, though, they predict values of 1.5 and 2.0, respectively, which are higher than those of our models. Ciesla et al. (2024), using spectral energy distribution modeling with the CIGALE code and assuming a non-parametric star formation history on the JADES public catalog, found $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle \sim 1.2$ in the range $6.5 < z < 10.5$, which is fairly consistent with our *bursty-sn* model. Finally, Pallottini & Ferrara (2023) analyzed 245 galaxies from the SERRA simulation suite at $z \sim 7.7$, finding a $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ of 0.61. We note, though, that the method employed for this evaluation differs from that used in our study and other works (see appendix A for more details). In general, we can conclude that the *bursty-sn* model typically aligns well with most constraints from the literature across all halo populations. However,

at lower redshifts the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models better match many of these constraints. This might indicate a possible transition in supernova feedback models at a particular redshift, highlighting how the regulation of star formation evolves as galaxies mature and the cosmic environment changes.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this study we investigate the role played by SN feedback in driving the variability of the UV LF as detected by JWST at high-redshift using the suite of radiation hydrodynamic simulations SPICE. These include three models for SN feedback, which differ in terms of energy and timing of the explosion: *bursty-sn*, *smooth-sn*, and *hyper-sn*. The *bursty-sn* model, characterized by intense and episodic supernova explosions, shows the highest SFR variability, leading to significant fluctuations in UV luminosity. However, attributing this directly to feedback alone is difficult, as feedback is a root cause but not the sole factor influencing these behaviors. In contrast, the *smooth-sn* model, despite injecting more energy overall, exhibits more stable SFRs and lower UV LF variability, likely due to a more stable ISM, possibly supported by the presence of more massive bulges that dynamically stabilize the system. The *hyper-sn* model shows intermediate behavior, with higher variability at early times due to HN effects, but it converges toward the *smooth-sn* behavior at lower redshifts as the fraction of HN events decreases. This illustrates that the UVLF variability we observe results from a complex interplay of feedback, gravitational potential, and morphological differences.

We observe a fairly good agreement between all models and the observed UV luminosity functions across all redshifts analyzed. Regarding variability, we find that it depends strongly on halo mass, with smaller halos experiencing larger fluctuations. This is likely due to their shallower gravitational potentials, which make them more susceptible to the disruptive effects of supernova feedback. This dependence is the same in all models, which also exhibit a very similar slope of the UV LF variability vs halo mass relation (ie. $\sigma_{UV}^{dust} - M_{halo}$), although the *bursty-sn* model produces larger median values of σ_{UV}^{dust} , as well as a larger scatter due to its more disruptive effect.

We also analyze the redshift evolution of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ across different halo mass bins, finding that smaller halos in the lowest mass bin exhibit higher values due to their sensitivity to feedback effects. Both the *smooth-sn* and *hyper-sn* models demonstrate a consistent trend in σ_{UV}^{dust} at lower redshifts, although the latter shows slightly higher variability than the former at $z \geq 10$. Furthermore, the variability of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ remains consistent across the entire redshift range (with a slightly decreasing feature), which is influenced by complex combined effect of deeper gravitational potential with decreasing redshift as well as increasing dynamical timescales that allow SN feedback to regulate the ISM more effectively. In contrast, the *bursty-sn* model shows an initial increase in σ_{UV}^{dust} from $z \approx 10$ to $z \approx 6$ before declining and consistently exhibits the highest average values of $\langle \sigma_{UV}^{dust} \rangle$ across all masses and redshifts, indicating greater fluctuations in star formation compared to the other models.

Although already noted, our work based on the comparison of simulations differing only for the SN feedback prescription clearly shows the impact that this has on the variability of star formation and luminosity in the early Universe. More specifically, median variabilities of the SFR and the dust attenuated UV LFs of are typical in the *bursty-sn* model, where the strong feedback injection causes a very bursty star formation. This, in turn, could account for the diverse

range of galactic brightness observed in recent deep-field surveys, such as those conducted by the JWST. Conversely, the smoother star formation history typically obtained in the smooth-sn model fails to induce a large variability, with typical values of σ . The hyper-sn model is in between the other two, although its characteristics are very similar to those of the smooth-sn one, with

We should note here that, there are certain limitations in SPICE despite the very advanced modeling of the various processes involved in galaxy formation and evolution. In particular, the relatively small box size constrains our ability to capture the full range of bright galaxies, particularly at the bright end of the UV LF. Additionally, the simplified treatment of dust and its interaction with UV radiation may lead to a mis-representation of its effects, especially in the more massive, dust-rich systems. Also, exploring alternative feedback mechanisms, such as cosmic rays, could provide further insights into the complex interplay between star formation and feedback in shaping the early universe's galaxy population. The mass and the spatial resolution of SPICE and the low temperature cooling implemented are also significant limitations.

In summary, this study highlights the pivotal role of supernova feedback in driving the variability of the UV LF in high-redshift galaxies, and how our understanding of the complex processes governing galaxy formation and evolution in the early universe can be advanced by refining theoretical models and utilizing new observational datasets.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The final data products from this study will be shared on reasonable request to the authors.

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Figure A1. Comparison of distribution for SFR computed from the temporal evolution of the most massive halo at $z = 5$ as shown in figure 3. The solid curves represent the results obtained using our method, while the dashed curves show the results from the method proposed by Pallottini & Ferrara (2023). In the inset, we quote the values of σ_{SFR} for these two methods.

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APPENDIX A: COMPARISON BETWEEN DIFFERENT METHOD FOR COMPUTING σ_{UV}

In this section, we examine how different methods of computing variability provide distinct insights into the same quantity and how these differences affect the interpretation of results. Specifically, we compare the standard approach adopted in the main text with the method proposed by Pallottini & Ferrara (2023) (hereafter referred to as PF23). We begin by analyzing the temporal evolution of the SFR for the most massive halo at $z = 5$ across all three SN feedback models, as illustrated in figure 3. Each curve is fitted with a third-order polynomial on a log-linear scale, following the technique used

by PF23. The stochastic variability of the SFR is then quantified by computing the residuals, defined as $\delta_{\text{SFR}} = \log_{10}(\text{SFR}/\text{SFRfit})$, from which we derive the standard deviation, σ_{SFR} . The results of this approach are compared with the standard method presented in Section 3.2 and summarized in Figure A1. We observe that the SFR distribution using the PF23 method is slightly shifted toward higher values across all models compared to the standard method. This shift is reflected in the slightly higher values of σ_{SFR} , with 0.39 for bursty-sn, 0.17 for smooth-sn, and 0.19 for hyper-sn, each exceeding the standard method’s results by approximately $\Delta(\sigma_{\text{SFR}}) \sim 0.04 - 0.05$.

The key difference lies in the PF23 method’s focus on the temporal evolution of individual halos up to the redshift of interest, which emphasizes fluctuations around the median curve for each halo’s evolution. In contrast, generally the variability is computed by examining deviations from a global median trend across a sample of halos at each redshift or time step. This distinction leads to a fundamentally different interpretation of the underlying variability being measured, with the PF23 method offering a more detailed view of individual halo evolution over time. When computing the redshift evolution of variability using PF23 method, it is essential to consider fluctuations from the time of halo formation up to the redshift of interest, rather than just within a specific time interval. This approach captures variability along the entire temporal evolution, providing a cumulative understanding that differs from a snapshot analysis at a single redshift (or within a specific redshift bin). Consequently, this method offers insights into how scatter integrates over broader epochs, contrasting with the more traditional redshift-by-redshift analysis.

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